

DOES PENSION FUNDS INVESTMENT AFFECT NIGERIAN CAPITAL MARKET?

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Abstract

This study examined whether or not Pension Fund Investment has an impact on Nigerian Capital Market (equity and bonds) using data 2010Q1 - 2023Q1. The study adopted secondary (i.e. time series) data obtained from sources like Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), Debt Management Office (DMO), Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) and National Pension Commission (PenCom) quarterly reports. Four variables were used in the study which were debt outstanding (Dout), Market Capitalization of stock (MKT), Pension Fund Assets (PFA) and Monetary Policy Rate (MPR). The variables were subjected to unit root test and they were all stationary at different order of I(0) and I(1). Since the Variables were not all stationary at level but a mixed series, the ARDL bound test of cointegration was used to test for cointegration among them. Using the bound test, the variables were found to be cointegrated at 5% level of significance. The ARDL result indicated that; Pension Fund Investments and other independent variables has a significant impact on the capital (Debt and Equity). From the findings the study recommended that the governments should ensure the sustainability of the Contributory Pension Scheme to have a pool of funds that can provide long-term financing to both the public and private sectors of the economy. The study also recommends adequate regulations of the investments of the pension funds' assets for the benefit of the contributors.

Keywords: Bonds, Contributory Pension, Equity, Market Capitalization, Pension Fund Investment.

JEL Classification: G1, G230, G240.

INTRODUCTION

The Nigerian Pension Industry had been undergoing a series of reforms for over one and half decades, as it is considered a catalyst for economic growth and development. The reforms were largely necessitated due to the increase in the number of retirees and government liabilities, which led to inadequate government budgetary allocation for pensions that resulted in excessive delays in payment of public sector pensioners (underfunded), non-adherence to the laws guiding private sector pension and the shortcomings of the of old age support mechanisms.

Some of the objectives of the reforms were to address the above mention challenges, expand coverage to include the non-formal sector, and ensure income security in old age for the populace. It was also targeted at developing some macroeconomic aspects such as financial markets, financial inclusion, and quality labor that are expected to facilitate economic growth & development as well as provide resources for the non-working population (retirees) without putting undue burden on the working population.

In realizing the pension goals, the industry initially relied upon Pay-As-You-Go (PAYG) scheme, which seems manageable as there were few retirees then. However, cost rise when the number of retirees increased, hence the dependency ratio rises faster than the passivity ratio. The PAYG was therefore criticized for being vulnerable to the effects of an increasing number of retirees, this makes PAYG engender economic distortion and unsuitable for retirees such as those on early retirements, disability pensions, evasion, and distinctive to save (Davis, 1998). However, the recently introduce Contributory Pension Scheme (CPS) offer better incentives for the development of capital and labor markets in Nigeria.

The Pension Reform Act (PRA 2004) was first enacted into law in the year 2004 and was later amended in 2014 PRA (2014), which is now in effect. The act which introduced the CPS, covers employees in both the public and the private sector. Under the scheme, the employee contributes a minimum of 8%, while the employer contributes a minimum of 10% of the employee's monthly total emolument. In addition, an employer may elect to bear the entire burden of the pension contribution, provided that the total contribution shall not be less than 18% of the employee's monthly emoluments as required by the provisions of the PRA 2014.

The Act mandates every employee to open a Retirement Savings Account (RSA) in his name with a PFA of his choice. It also, allows for voluntary contributions to be made by either active members, retirees, or those exempted from the scheme to the maximum of 33% of the voluntary contributor's monthly salary. It further highlighted that pension contributions are tax-deductible expenses, voluntary contributions made by employees or retirees could only be taxed (income earned) at the point of withdrawal where the withdrawal is made five years from the date of the contribution.

National Pension Commission (the Commission), the agency established to supervise and regulate the pension sector in Nigeria, licensed three types of players to undertake different mandates in the management and administration of the Pension Funds. These players include the Pension Fund Administrators (PFAs) licensed for the management and administration of the Pension Funds, while the Pension Fund Custodians (PFCs) are licensed to keep custody of the funds.

The third player is the Closed Pension Fund Administrators (CPFAs), which are part of the pension schemes in the private sector before the introduction of the Contributory Pension Scheme that was allowed to continue subject to guidelines issued by the Commission. The CPFAs operate mostly defined Benefits Schemes, with guarantees from the sponsor companies over any funding deficit. The separation of the responsibilities of managing/administration and keeping custody of the fund between the PFAs and PFCs is one of the safeguards of the pension industry in Nigeria.

The Contributory Pension Scheme in Nigeria is funded by 18% of the employer/employee monthly contributions to the RSA of the employee managed by the PFA and the contributions from fund sponsors to either an Approved Existing Scheme (AES) or CPFA scheme in respect of the members of the respective funds. The act required that all pension fund contributions collected are to be invested in line with guidelines and regulations issued by the Commission.

The Commission had developed a guideline for Pension Fund Investment called Regulation on Investment of Pension Fund Assets (Investment Regulation). The Investment regulation serves as a guide for the optimum investment of pension assets by PFAs putting into consideration the concept of diversification, reducing volatility, and expected return. Some of the allowable asset classes include; Capital markets investment (Stocks and Bonds), Money market instruments (Term Deposit and Commercial Papers), and specialized funds (Mutual Funds, Private Equity and Infrastructure Funds), amongst others.

According to data obtained from the Commission website, the pension asset witnessed a weighted growth of 3.93% in Q1: 2023 from N14.99 trillion as of 31 December 2022 to N15.58 trillion as of 31 March 2023. The industry also witnesses a 0.85% growth in the number of registered RSAs from 9.86 million as of 31 December 2022 to 9.95 as of 31 March 2023. A review of the aggregate total contribution of N8.70 trillion from inception to date (2004-2023), shows that the public sector contributions constituted 52.03%, while that of the private sector constituted the remaining 47.97%. Considering the huge size of pension fund assets in Nigeria, there was a strong demand for an investigation into how the investment of pension fund assets impacts economic growth and development with a particular focus on the capital market. Pension funds are adjudged to provide long-term funds for economic development, giving the long-term investment horizon of the funds. For instance, Henshaw (2012) argues that pension funds investment could provide long-term funds for the economic and social development of the country. However, there were teething challenges to the dearth of investment outlets. The challenges were linked to the investment constraints enshrined in the investment regulation that requires pension fund assets to be invested in high-quality instruments. For instance, Tsado and Gunu (2011), pointed out that the top twenty companies in the capital market have more than 70% of the total market capitalization, necessitating a pool of pension funds chasing few quality investments. However, this study is of the view that pension fund investments contribute to the performance of the capital market, a subject which received little attention from researchers.

Furthermore, Nigerian government and entrepreneurs had faced several challenges in raising funds for financing long-term projects, due to the lack of savings and depth in the Nigerian Capital market. This led to entrepreneurs relying on bank loans for long-term financing at ridiculous interest rates while the national and sub-national governments relied on foreign loans for project financing, which exposed the country to foreign exchange dynamics. Since the commencement of the Contributory Pension Scheme in 2004, the scheme had accumulated large assets amounting to around ₦15.6 trillion as of 31 March 2023. The fund is now the largest pool of funds in the country available for long-term financing to both the public and private sectors. This has caught the attention of financial market players and led to some researchers conducting an impact analysis of pension funds in the Nigerian capital market. However, most of the researchers restricted their scope of study to a market capitalization of debt, ignoring the value of debt outstanding that could give a better insight into debt issuance by government and corporate issuers. This study therefore, focused on the impact of Pension Fund Investment on the Nigerian Capital Market using Auto Regressive Distributed Lag Model.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The theoretical framework which links the capital market to pension funds development, as savings and investment platforms, include the opportunity to provide long-term capital to employers of labor and realize or liquidate holdings when pension liabilities crystallize. Notable among the theories are (i) the loanable fund theory which contends that (*ceteris paribus*) interest rate is determined by the interaction of savers and investors, such that investment varies inversely with the rate of interest, while savings is directly related to the interest rate. (ii) the portfolio theory on the other hand contends that in the real world, financial investments are subject to systematic risk, such that there is a limit to diversification (Megginston et al., 2007). While identifying interest rate as a potential pension risk Scheuenstuhl (2012) again reviews that a prudently managed pension fund requires being consistently forward-looking in managing all risk factors that drive the outcome of the pension assets and liabilities in a capital market.

Several empirical types of research were carried out to find the link between pension fund investments and capital market performance. For instance, Bayar, Gavriletea, Danuletiu, Danuletiu, & Sakar, (2022) found that stock markets foster economic growth through meeting the fund requirements of the firms by individual and institutional investors. Pension funds and insurance companies with their long-term investment horizon are critical institutional investors in capital markets. Therefore, this article explores the effect of pension funds and insurance companies on stock market development in 15 emerging market economies over the 2004–2019 period through panel cointegration and causality tests. The causality analysis revealed that stock market development had a significant impact on pension funds and the insurance sector in the short term. However, the cointegration analysis revealed that pension funds had a positive effect on stock market development in Brazil, Chile, Hungary, Mexico, Peru, and South Africa and the insurance sector had a positive impact on stock market development in Chile, Indonesia, Korea Republic, Philippines, and South Africa in the long term.

Daradkah, & Al-Hamdoun, (2021) investigate the dynamic relationship between pension funds and development of capital market in Jordan over the period 1980–2017. Autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) approaches for co-integration (bounds test) are employed to achieve the objectives of the study. Using annual data, the results indicate no statistically significant relationship between pension funds and development of capital market on the short run. However, the co-integration tests show a statistically significant long-run equilibrium relationship between pension funds and development of capital market regardless of whether capital market development was measured by market depth or market liquidity. Moreover, the co-integration tests show a statistically significant long-run equilibrium relationship between economic growth, and interest rate and development of capital market regardless of whether capital market development was measured by market depth or market liquidity. These findings have important implications for academics, investment managers, and policy makers in Jordan. Babalos, & Stavroyiannis, (2020) investigate the dynamic interaction between stock market development and pension funds' investment in equities. Results are derived from a panel VAR of 29 countries. Our main finding is that pension fund investments in equities enhance stock

market development. Moreover, there is significant bidirectional Granger causality between stock market development and pension funds' investment in equities. The forecast error variance decompositions validate the importance of pension funds for stock market development. Our analysis has important implications for the design of future government policies regarding pension fund systems and for the well-functioning of capital markets.

Grujić, (2019) explores the impact of pension funds on market development. The study links the credit rating of a country and the development of the financial market. It equally established a link between the structure and size of pension funds and the development of financial markets across countries. The development of the market is expressed with the help of the FD index, the size of pension funds as a size related to GDP, the structure of pension funds, as a participation of shares or bonds in relation to total assets and in relation to GDP, and the size of funds is expressed in relation to the GDP of the country. Qualitative research techniques, such as analysis, comparative analysis, correlation between the two observed variables and synthesis were conducted. The selected group of countries was based on two criteria based on data from 2018: OECD countries and the others. The study explained the possibilities that pension funds with their structure and size offer to the development of the financial market in the country. The result shows that pension funds can provide a significant support for financing the development of the country, local communities, but that between certain phenomena, such as the size and structure of funds and the size of the economy and the development of the financial market, there is only a poor determination. This paper has intentions to offer a special strategy for creating a portfolio and it is an initial step towards further analysis and directions on the portfolio management.

Rocholl & Niggemann (2010) provide evidence that a country's pension system is an important determinant for the development of its capital markets. Employing a unique event list of 87 pension funding reforms in 57 countries between 1976 and 2007, we find that pension funding reforms lead to larger stock and corporate bond markets relative to the time before the reforms and relative to other countries without such reforms. This effect is particularly driven by an increase in the post-reform primary market issuing activity and cannot be explained by a simultaneous political move to more market-oriented reforms in these countries in general. We find that the effect is particularly significant in emerging markets with a priori less developed capital markets. Further evidence from a cross-sectional analysis suggests that the degree of pension funding is an important determinant of the cross-country variation in capital market development. It remains robust even after controlling for other important determinants of capital market development such as legal origin and trade openness.

Blake (2003) examines the accumulation and distributional phases of the U.K pension system and argued that whether a system is of the DC scheme or the DB scheme, appropriate financial instruments and investment strategy are more critical than both the financial market structure and the nature of the financial institutions in driving successful private sector pensions. The study discovered that in many markets including the U.K., pension fund managers underperformed the market. Borsch-Supan et al. (2004) use panel data to examine how population aging and pension reform impact savings behavior in continental Europe,

comprising France, Germany, and Italy. These countries are noted for large and ailing pay-as-you-go public pension systems; relatively thin capital markets and relatively low capital performance. The study found a positive link between the aging population syndrome to savings growth by the young generation, passing-through to the capital market, with beneficial side effects on productivity and aggregate growth. Wang (2004) did a non-parametric study on China's pension reform and capital market development and found a correlation between a funded pension system's boost of the capital market and the existence of appropriate financial infrastructure and effective financial regulations.

Meggison et al. (2007)'s findings reveal that countries that rely mainly on compulsory privately financed pension tends to have a larger capital market and are most efficient (e.g. United States, United Kingdom; Netherlands; and Switzerland), compared to others, such as continental European countries that rely on the state-run unfunded pension system, who are characterized by relatively smaller market. Davis (1998) analyzes the impact of pension reforms on the financial sector development and argues that generally, the type of pension reform instituted has a stronger influence on the effects of capital markets development and stronger stability support, warning that a non-competitive regulatory system that restricts portfolio investments is likely to affect adversely the beneficial effect of the funds on the capital market. Nwanne (2015) examined the impact of the contributory pension scheme on economic growth in Nigeria for the period 2004-2012. The objectives of the study were to determine the impact of pension funds on economic growth and as well as to ascertain the impact of pension savings mobilized on economic growth. The study used an Ex-post-facto research design. The ordinary Least Square Regression method was used in data analysis. The study finds that pension funds have a negative and significant impact on economic growth while pension savings had a positive and significant impact on economic growth. The finding implies that the contributory pension scheme has achieved the objective of using pension funds to provide long-term capital that will promote economic growth. It also implies that pension savings contribution is low an indication of low coverage of the scheme. It was recommended that investment outlets of pension funds should be increased and efforts should be intensified to ensure greater compliance and mobilization of savings from contributors.

Gunu and Tsado (2012) studied the contributory pension system as a tool for economic growth in Nigeria. The study used descriptive statistics, percentages, and charts to analyze the data collected. Their findings revealed that the contributory pension scheme has begun to contribute to the increase in the growth of the Nigerian capital market and economic growth. Dostal (2010) studied pension reforms in Nigeria for the period 2006 to 2010. The study finds that the funded pension system has not had any significant impact on the development of the financial market and that real sector investment was not boosted by savings from the pension scheme. Also, the macroeconomic credibility of the government has declined. The findings implied that the regulatory environment failed to encourage interaction between pension reform and economic reform while problems of regulation within the system have also contributed to a lack of reform credibility. Abdulkadir, Magdalene Ugwuatuamara (2018) studied the Impact of Contributory Pension Schemes on Workers' Investments and Savings in Nigeria. The findings implied This implies that a unit percent increase in contributory pension funds will contribute 5.7% to

workers' savings and investment in the economy. There is also a positive relationship between interest rates, savings rates, and workers' savings and investments in Nigeria. The study reveals that a unit percentage increase in interest rates and saving rates contributes 53% and 25% rise in workers' savings and investments.

METHODOLOGY

The correlational research design was adopted to examine the effect of pension funds' investments on the Nigerian capital market performance. The choice of this design is informed by the effectiveness of the method in investigating the relationships among theoretically related variables. Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Model. The ARDL establishes a long-run and short-run interaction between exchange rate volatility and inflation rate. ARDL belongs to a category of multivariate time series model commonly used for data where the underlying variables have a long-run stochastic trend, also known as co-integration. It is a theoretically driven approach useful for estimating both short-term and long-term effect of one-time series on another. The study used secondary data from different sources: Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) quarterly economic reports and financial Statistical Bulletin, The Debt Management Office quarterly reports and the quarterly publications of the Pension Commission of Nigeria. The data collected from the sources is a time series for the period 53 quarters (Q1: 2010-Q2:2023). Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Model. The ARDL to establish a long-run and short-run interaction between exchange rate volatility and inflation rate. ARDL belongs to a category of multivariate time series model commonly used for data where the underlying variables have a long-run stochastic trend, also known as co-integration. It is a theoretically driven approach useful for estimating both short-term and long-term effect of one-time series on another. The choice of the model is informed by the fact that the time series has mixed order of integration but the disturbances are not auto correlated; thus, other OLS regression estimators' models may be biased. The paper on also conducted some robustness tests to ensure the reliability of the results. These tests include the test of serial correlation and heteroscedasticity.

ARDL bound test of co-integration by Pesaran (2001) was carried out. The ARDL approach to co-integration is recommended in cases where the variables have different order of integration that is I(0) and I(1). The ARDL procedure involves two stages. In the first stage, the null hypothesis of no co-integration ($H_0: \theta_1 = \theta_2 = \theta_3 = \theta_4 = \theta_5 = 0$) is tested against the alternative hypothesis of co-integration ($H_1: \theta_1 \neq 0, \theta_2 \neq 0, \theta_3 \neq 0, \theta_4 \neq 0, \theta_5 \neq 0$). Testing co-integration relationship is based on the F-statistic. Since the asymptotic distribution of this F-statistic is non-standard irrespective of whether the variables are I(0) or I(1), Narayan (2005) tabulated two sets of critical values which are appropriate for the studies with small sample size ranging from 30 to 80 observations. In this sense, one set assumes that all variables are I(0) and other set assumes that all variables are I(1). This provides a bound covering all possible classifications of the variables. If the calculated F-statistic lies above the upper level of the bound, the H_0 is rejected, supporting co-integration relationship. If the calculated F-statistic lies below the lower level of the bound, then the H_0 cannot be rejected, indicating lack of co-integration.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The descriptive statistics for the study is presented in Table 1; The table shows that the total market capitalization of equity and debt outstanding has a mean of 4.08% and 3.99% with a standard deviation of 0.18 and 0.214 respectively. The table presents a minimum and maximum value of 3.54% & 3.75% and 4.36% & 4.47% 5.49% respectively.

The range between the minimum and maximum is wide, it implies a stable performance as the standard deviation indicated that there is no wide dispersion of the data from the mean value. Furthermore, the table also revealed that logDout, LogPFA and MPR are negatively skewed to the left. Only the value of MPR is mesokurtic in nature as the value of its kurtosis is greater than three, while other variables are platykurtic as the value of their kurtosis is less than three. The probability of the Jarque-Bera shows that all the variables were not normally distributed.

Table: 1 Descriptive Statistics

	LOGDOUT	LOGMCAP	LOGPFA	MPR
Mean	3.999427	4.081595	3.760093	12.08208
Median	4.035238	4.067690	3.775360	12.00000
Maximum	4.358880	4.471989	4.192636	18.00000
Minimum	3.539874	3.745499	3.188194	6.000000
Std. Dev.	0.213716	0.180895	0.290608	2.397477
Skewness	-0.199599	0.382570	-0.300539	-0.921742
Kurtosis	2.153179	2.797394	2.016036	4.511069
Jarque-Bera	1.935527	1.383492	2.935935	12.54723
Probability	0.379932	0.500701	0.230393	0.001885
Sum	211.9696	216.3245	199.2849	640.3500
Sum Sq. Dev.	2.375067	1.701598	4.391553	298.8905
Observations	53	53	53	53

The descriptive results from Table 1 above, also indicated that the average monetary policy rate (MPR) during the period is 12.08% (consumer price index) with a standard deviation of 2.40 and minimum and maximum values of 6% and 18% respectively.

This implies an increasing MPR trend during the period under review, as the analysis indicated that there was an increase in inflation of about 50% during the period, which usually affects savings and consequently investments. Similarly, table 1 above showed that the Pension Fund Assets (PFA) during the period has an average value of 3.75% with a standard deviation of 0.2906% and minimum and maximum values of 3.188% and 4.192% respectively. This implies an increase in pension fund assets during the period from 3.188% in 2010 to 4.192% in the first quarter of 2023.

Unit Root Tests

Unit root test was conducted to determine the presence of stationarity or otherwise in the variables. The study employs the use of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) to test for ascertaining the stationarity of the variables.

Table 2: Dicky-Fuller Test for Unit Root

Variables	ADF@ level	ADF@ 1 st Diff	Order of Integ
L Dout	-4.169987	-	I(0)
LPFA	-1.882956	-8.206620	I(1)
LOGMCAP	-2.443889	-9.762116	I(1)
MPR	-2.191061	-7.422185	I(1)

Author’s computation result using E-views 10

Augmented Dickey fuller test of the unit root also employed the test of null hypothesis technique (that the variable has a unit root, i.e. non-stationary). Table 2 indicates the presence of unit root in LPFA, Log MCAP, and MPR models at levels because the p-value of the t-statistics is not statistically significant. On the other hand, the table shows the absence of unit root in L Dout, as the p-values of the test statistic are significant. Thus, the null hypothesis that the data has a unit root is rejected. The problem of unit root in the time series affects the OLS results, as such the study might use more generalized techniques to address the problem.

ARDL Bound Test Approach to Cointegration

The bound test approach to cointegration seeks to confirm if there is a long run relationship among the variables in the model. This is done by testing if their coefficients are equal to zero in our estimated model or not. The F-Statistic value from the bound test and the critical value bounds as revealed by the regression result using E-views 10 is presented in the table 3:

Table 3: F-Bounds Test for Cointegration

F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship		
Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
			Asymptotic: n=1000	
F-statistic	5.744504	10%	2.01	3.1
K	3	5%	2.45	3.63
		2.5%	2.87	4.16
		1%	3.42	4.84

Author’s computation result using E-views 10

The bound test is the test to determine if there is a long-run relationship as a null hypothesis says that; there is no long-run relationship, according to the value of F-statistics, first case; if this value is lower than I(0) we don’t reject the null hypothesis and there is no long-run relationship, second one; if this value greater than I(1) we reject the null hypothesis and we can indicate that there is a long relationship, the last case; if this value lies between two bounds we cannot judge. Here, we are in the second case as the value of the F-statistic is greater than the upper bound which includes that there is a long-run relationship at all levels of significance 1%, 5%, and 10%.

Short Run Dynamics and Error Correction Representation

After confirming the existence of a long-run relationship between the gross domestic product growth rate and its explanatory variables in the study, it is pertinent to estimate both the error

correction mechanism form of the model together with its long run form. The error correction model was first used by Sargan (1964) and after this popularized by Engle and Granger (1987). Also, the diagnostic tests are examined from the unrestricted error correction (bounds test) model. These include Lagrange multiplier test of residual serial correlation, Ramsey's RESET test using the square of the fitted values for correct functional form (no misspecification), Jarque-Bera normality test based on the skewness and kurtosis measures of the residuals and Breusch-Godfrey heteroscedasticity test based on the regression of squared residuals on the original regressors of the model. The results are presented in the table 4;

Table 4 above shows that there are significant effects of the lags of the pension fund asset on the capital market variables. We have a highly significant effect of the first lag of MCAP, PFA, and DOUT, the second lag of MCAP, at a 5% level of confidence, and also the third lag of DOUT.

Table 4: The result of the ARDL (2,2,4,0) Model

Variable	Coefficient	Std.Error	t-Statistics	significant
MCAP(-1))	-0.266142	0.105721	-2.517404	yes
PFA	5.317262	0.879784	6.043825	yes
LOGPFA(-1))	0.829886	0.535574	1.549525	no
DOUT	-0.579991	0.272911	-2.125206	no
DOUT(-1))	-0.134488	0.303579	-0.443008	no
DOUT(-2)	-0.094216	0.303444	-0.310488	no
LOGDOUT(-3))	1.538713	0.294784	5.219793	yes
CointEq(-1)*	-0.050638	0.010170	-4.979163	yes
Adjusted R-squared: 0.589889: AIC:-3.352806: SC=-3.043937 HQC;-3.235621:DW:1.82				

Author's computation result using E-views 10

The CointEq(-1) shows how much of the disequilibrium is being corrected, that is, the extent to which any disequilibrium in the previous period is being adjusted in the current point. A positive coefficient indicates a divergence, while a negative coefficient indicates convergence. If the estimate of CointEq(-1) = 1, then 100% of the adjustment takes place within the period, or the adjustment is instantaneous and full, if the estimate of CointEq(-1) = 0.5, then 50% of the adjustment takes place each period/year. CointEq(-1) = 0, shows that there is no adjustment, and to claim that there is a long-run relationship does not make sense. In this case, the CointEq(-1) is a negative sign and highly significant which indicates convergence and the study can conclude that 5% of adjustment from the short run to long-run is taken place quarterly.

Table: 5 Serial Correlation and Heteroskedasticity tests

TEST	CHI-SQUARED	P-VALUE
Lagrange Multiplier (LM) for Serial Correlation	2.891407	0.2356
Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey for Heteroskedasticity	9.939242	0.2693

Author's computation result using E-views 10"

As widely used for checking the serial correlation of the residuals, the LM test is used and it is confirmed that there is no longer a serial correlation between residuals. As shown in Table 5;

the null hypothesis that there is no serial correlation is not rejected at level 0.05 which means that there is no evidence for serial correlation in the residuals term of the estimated model. Also, Table 5 shows that there is no heteroscedasticity (or the variance is constant) in the residuals since we don't reject the null hypothesis of no heteroscedasticity at level 0.05.

CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Four variables were used in the study which were Debt Outstanding (Dout), Pension Fund Asset (PFA), Market Capitalization of Stocks (Mkt Cap) and Monetary Policy Rate (MPR). The variables were subjected to unit root test and they were all stationary at different orders of $I(0)$ and $I(1)$. Since the Variables were not all stationary at level but a mixed series, the ARDL bound test of cointegration was used to test for cointegration among them. Using the bound test, the variables were found to be cointegrated at a 1% level of significance. The ARDL result indicated that; Firstly, Pension Fund Investments has a significant impact market capitalization of stocks in the Nigerian Capital Market. Secondly, Pension Fund Investments also have a significant impact on debt issuance in Nigeria in the long-run, with the impact also statistically significant.

Consistent with the findings from the analysis conducted, the study concludes that there is a significant positive relationship between pension funds' investments and the growth of the capital market in Nigeria after the 2004 major industry reform. Specifically, the study concludes that total pension investments in Nigeria have a positive effect on the Nigerian Capital Market. Moreover, the study concludes that the interaction of macroeconomic indicators such as interest rate, inflation rate, and GDP growth with pension investments affects capital market performance significantly.

Recommendations

The study recommends that governments should ensure the sustainability of the Contributory Pension Scheme to have a pool of funds that can provide long-term financing to both the public and private sectors of the economy. The study also recommends adequate regulations of the investments of the pension funds' assets for the benefit of the contributors. In addition, the Capital Market Regulators should be encouraged to have water tight regulatory environment in other to protect pension fund assets deployed into the market to ensure safety and fair return.

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